

Modelling centres/groups survey: spin up metrics, ocean regridding, BECCS, Rapid Evaluation Tool

*CMIP International Project Office
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Responding centres/groups

19 modelling centres/groups responded to the survey by the deadline on 28 June 2024.

Spin up metrics

Would your centre/group be willing to share details of your spin up and a limited set of timeseries metrics?

■ YES ■ NO

Would your centre/group be willing to share details of your spin up and a limited set of timeseries metrics?

Yes/No	Comment
Yes	The time (in the models) required for spin-up to reach equilibrium is an important issue.
Yes	Yes, we would not put out the full data request, but basic variables like surface temperature of 3d mean ocean temperature could be provided. Clear guidance on best practice for spin-up, and the scientific rationale, would likely be very useful. For our centre, spinning up to equilibrium is has always been important for scientific credibility.
Yes	Ready to share time-series metrics
Yes	We are available to share a limited set of time series metrics related to our spin up.
Yes	We are convinced that the spin-up is an important stage and that more transparency is necessary
Yes	At standard resolution, we typically conduct a spin-up of 1000 to 2000 years before starting the actual piControl simulation. The goal is to achieve a quasi-equilibrium state with minimum long-term drift. Metrics we pay close attention include net radiation at the top of the atmosphere which should be near zero (typically less than 0.1 W/m ² on average); global mean surface air temperature should exhibit no drift and have a reasonable global mean value; maximum and minimum sea-ice extent should be stable. We also monitor evolution of global ocean heat content aiming for near zero drift in upper and intermediate water masses and minimum for bottom water. We occasionally perform minor tuning or changes during the spin-up, either to minimize drift or introduce a last-minute fix.
Yes	We can share some integrals of atmospheric and oceanic fields for spin-up runs.
Yes	Yes, we are willing to share details of our spin up method and sample timeseries metrics.
Yes	It is important to be transparent about equilibration procedure adopted for each component and for the coupled system as a whole.

Would your centre/group be willing to share details of your spin up and a limited set of timeseries metrics?

Yes/No	Comment
Yes	We understand the motivations for setting up the WG and are willing to contribute by sharing some details of our procedure.
Yes	We would be happy to contribute to the spin-up activity.
Yes	We would like to share details our spin-up run.
Yes	For CMIP6, the relevant discussion was published in Kelley et al, 2020 and Miller et al 2021.
Yes	This is a very important and exciting new activity for CMIP!
Yes	Yes. We will share details of the spin up and some variables.
Yes	Access to data may be difficult.
No	<i>We have no more experience in spin up.</i>
No	<i>We are still developing the version that will be used in CMIP7. We can provide information and data once the version and set up is fixed.</i>
No	<i>Actually, I am not sure whether I can provide a proper data what this group want. I mean that we are tuning our model with several physical parameter now and we will examine whether theses outputs could be reasonable and preparable to move to piControl run within this year, if possible. So I am not sure I have enough time to pick up the proper data you want and provide them to you. Also our spin-up and model tuning test needs very huge storage resources, therefore we should limit data storage for saving and managing whole CMIP data sets of our own model. I think this would be not big, but also not small problem in terms of developing and managing the whole system including the climate model.</i>

Ocean re-gridding

Is your centre/group able to supply horizontally regridded ocean data on a lat-lon or Mercator grid (check all that apply)?

For those replying “Neither”, the reason given was:

- Ocean model grid is tripolar
- Technically, can interpolate, but cannot warrant the quality of the interpolation for all needs (in particular for velocities and transport).

If the option to provide data on a 1/4 degree grid were available (versus 1 degree), would your centre/group be able to provide data on this grid?

- Yes, all variables
- Yes, a few variables
- No

Concerns outlined included:

- We feel that providing data on the native grid is important. We cannot afford to ship two sets of data, at least for many variables. We do have the ability to regrid. Better guidance about the needs and preferences of the community would be useful in choosing what form of the data to submit.
- The duplication of oceanic gridded data would increase the data volume to a level that could be difficult to manage.
- As our ocean model is coarser than a 1/4 degree grid, we do not want to provide data at an artificially finer resolution. Moreover, this will constitute an unnecessary data storage and associated carbon emission.
- It would depend on the level of reprocessing and documentation required for CMIP standards.
- We would consider regridding higher resolution data down to 1/4 degree, but do not intend to regrid 1 degree data to such a grid. We plan to support regridding of surface fields (or any 2-dimensional quantities e.g. MLD) but the same is far more challenging for 3-dimensional datasets and this would depend on the list of variables requested. As such we are unlikely to be able to regrid 3D fields on the Fast Track timescales.
- For 1/4, we submitted data on our native 1/4 tripolar grid. Some work would be involved in converting 1/4 data to a lat-lon grid. For transports on our native tri-polar grid, we do not rotate the transport in the bipolar Arctic to align with lat/lon lines. We kept it "y-ward" which is on the model native grid.

Is your centre/group able to provide precalculated meridional fluxes, MOC, depth-integrated transport?

The two centres who responded “No”:

- Model is still under development and is unclear at the moment if can provide these.
- No reason provided.

Other comments (those responding “Yes”) included:

- We would be able to provide meridional fluxes, but for now, these are not purely meridional as our ocean model provides mean over the grid vertices. It may be possible to provide true meridional averages, but additional work is necessary. We will implement true meridional averages depending on the time we have.
- Yes, for MOC. Not sure about meridional fluxes and depth-integrated transport.
- We shall elaborate the post processing routines to provide such fluxes outputs.

Are there any modifications to the CMIP6 standard vertical grid of 35 levels necessary?

Those centres responding “Yes” highlighted:

- The native model contains many more levels, particularly near the surface. More surface and near bottom resolution can be important for impact studies (e.g. low oxygen at the bottom).
- Our ocean model have 50 levels in the vertical.
- We will not be offering vertical regridding at this stage and (in our opinion) this has a lower priority than horizontal regridding. We may be able to provide this data at a later stage, but this will not be in time for the Fast Track.

BECCS

Representation of bioenergy crops and harvesting cycle

Does your model represent land use/land management?

Does your model represent anthropogenic carbon pools (specific pools with various turnover times)?

Does your model represent bioenergy plant functional types (PFT)?

Represent PFTs?	If yes, which bioenergy PFTs does your model include	If other, provide detail
Yes	C4 perennial grasses, plantation forests	
Yes	C4 perennial grasses, plantation forests	
Yes	C4 perennial grasses	
Yes	C4 perennial grasses	
Yes	C4 perennial grasses, plantation forests	Planting and harvesting dates, crop species (herbaceous and trees), transport and destination to processing facilities where efficiency can be calculated.

Represent PFTs?	If no, plans to account for this PFT if provided with LUH
No	Treat as crop
No	No answer
No	Treat as crop
No	Model does not represent BECCS
No	Treated as crop (as in CMIP6 version) for FastTrack, but potential new bio-energy PFTs for CMIP7 (post-Fast Track) version.
No	Treat as crop
No	Treat as crop
No	No current plans but proposed model development to implement deforestation from the LUH2-GCB could be coordinated with implementing a biofuel PFT and management if additional support is obtained.
No	No plan as yet
No	Treat as crop
No	

Is your, or will your, ESM be able to implement technical crop yield improvements?

If including forest plantations as a bioenergy feedstock, are these handled separately from forest plantations used for A/Reforestation and/or forestry/logging?

BECCS

Carbon capture

For models implementing bioenergy – plan to parameterise the efficiency of carbon capture?

- Only five centres/groups will implement bioenergy.
- Out of these only two plan to parameterise efficiency of carbon capture.

If (non-optimal) carbon capture efficiencies at the Bioenergy plants are represented, they would include:

- 12 centres do not know yet.
- Harvesting losses = 6 groups
- Reservoir losses = 3 groups
- Transportation/industrial losses = 1 group

Could your model incorporate land-use forcing that provides spatially explicit information to distinguish states/transitions of crops used for BECCS and those of crops used for energy purposes without storage (i.e. biofuels)?

Yes/No	Explanation for response
Yes	Our model has specific CFTs for BECCS and biofuels.
Yes	Land use transition maps provide information on states/transition of Miscanthus and switchgrass.
Yes	Our model would like to use the land-use forcing that provides the explicit information about crops.
Yes	We could add crop types as long as their specifications were provided in terms of physiological/ecological characteristics, planting and harvesting characteristics, fertilizer and irrigation needs if any.
Yes	Will try to do it
No	We are not sure about this, but we will follow the land model in CESM3.
No	Under development
No	It is not part of our primary scientific interests but ongoing discussions on how to implement, in particular for scenarios with high CDR
No	We assume that we would have to distinguish crops for food supply and those for bio-fuel. If that would not be the case, the answer would be yes.
No	It is not yet clear how we will deal with this
No	Our ESM currently has irrigation, which enhances photosynthetic uptake, but it has not simulated enhanced carbon density, yet (but could). Currently does not have fertilization or a crop harvest scheme, it could be implemented if support was obtained, Our model would not be spatially explicit and would most likely implement the biofuels as fractions of a crop type. Note that we aren't really clear how this would impact the climate (beyond the net fluxes) so question why this should be included in the GCMs as opposed to the IAMs.

The other centres responded that their models did not represent BECCS or did not provide an answer.

BECCS

Carbon storage

Can you currently, or are you planning to, implement an explicit carbon removal pool representing geological carbon storage in your model?

■ YES ■ NO

If yes, do you (or would you need to) differentiate between sources of stored carbon, e.g., from DACCS, BECCS, or ocean-based methods?

We would not differentiate them.

Yes. To clarify we do not track a geological pool, but we can remove CO₂ out the atmosphere (and it disappears out of the system).

Yes BECCS, DACCS and ocean CS methods are parametrized separately, and we are planning to keep track of the storage separated.

No

No

Explicit carbon removal is yet to be implemented. We can be flexible regarding differentiation between sources, if the relevant information is provided early enough

If no, explain how your model would account for removal of carbon from the system.

We are not sure about this, but we will follow the land model in CESM3.

It is prescribed

The model maintains a carbon budget. We currently do not have a mechanism for removal processes not explicitly in the model.

Our model does not remove atmospheric carbon.

Implicitly (as already done for CMIP6)

The carbon disappears - no need to track the geological pool. (in the same way that fossil emissions "appear" without needing to track or deplete a geological pool)

Carbon which is stored permanently in a reservoir would be removed from the model system.

Exogenous removal, diagnosed, but not prognostic.

Our model can be run now in a concentration mode only. So I think our model can be provided somewhat indirect information following the CDRMIP of CMIP6. Also we will try to move our model to be conducted in emission driven run next CMIP time.

This would need to be provided as a separate atmospheric CO₂ or land pool flux forcing as part of the scenario including spatial distribution.

We are not sure at this stage.

If you have an implemented carbon removal pool in your model or are currently implementing it, will this be in the fully coupled (emission-driven) model version that will be used for ScenarioMIP runs for the AR7 Fast Track?

Yes/No	Further detail
Yes, we will implement it aligned with AR7 Fast Track timelines	
Yes, we will implement it aligned with AR7 Fast Track timelines	
Yes, we will implement it aligned with AR7 Fast Track timelines	
Yes, we will implement it aligned with AR7 Fast Track timelines	The implementation will be very simple, such as adding infinite carbon pools as a prognostic variable where the removed carbons are delivered.
No, but we are currently implementing it or plan to in the near future	We could consider adding carbon to deeper layers of the ocean.
No, but we are currently implementing it or plan to in the near future	We are implementing it in a model which is different from the one that will be used in AR7 fast track, but our plan is to port it in the AR7 fast track model.

If the ESM-internal calculations/estimations of emissions / removals from BECCS is not included in ScenarioMIP, would you still be interested to investigate this within a separate MIP in the context of CMIP7?

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Yes/No	Further detail (where provided)
Yes	We are going to contribute to LUMIP, but we will try to implement it in the ScenarioMIP runs too.
Yes	We have not evaluated the ability of the model to do these things, but we could explore it. We find the questions a bit confusing, since in our view CDR etc is built into the scenarios already, at least for concentration driven runs (but could be represented as reductions in emissions in ESM runs too). Additional information would be useful on the plans.
Yes	This scientific question (including the one on crop yield improvement) is something of interest but we would see this question separated from ScenarioMIP (as it is now and given the current timeline). A separate activity would then make sense on a longer timeframe.
Yes	
Yes	We don't expect to have a representation of biofuels or BECCS in our core CMIP7 model. On a longer timescale, we would be interested in these processes using a CMIP7+ model.
Yes	
Yes	
Yes	
No	Maybe, depending on capabilities and resources.
No	Ongoing discussions about this...

Which additional information from IAMs and/or the land-use forcing data would you need to represent BECCS in a meaningful way within your model?

Would you need this (IAM or land use forcing) information in a specific format?

Additional open comments

- Would encourage further technical discussion on those topics, to guide our own developments. Besides, we would be happy to engage in discussions regarding additional forcings to be provided by CMIP7 for anthropogenic nitrogen emission (NH_3 , N_2O) coming from IAMs to be used for emission-driven simulations (historical and scenarios).
- Changes in distribution of biocrops need to be harmonized with historical distribution of land cover and land use similarly to what was done in CMIP6 LUH2 (Hurtt et al., 2020; <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/13/5425/2020/>), particularly gross transitions between land use types. Any information on soil management practices including enhanced rock weathering and soil carbon sequestration.
- It would be good to have the radiative forcing of the various forcings.

Rapid Evaluation Framework

Does your centre/group currently use any community model evaluation or benchmarking tools?

■ Yes

■ No

■ No, but we plan to within the CMIP7 timeframe (up to around 2030)

Currently use?	Tools currently used	Tools planned for use on CMIP7 timeline	Involvement in tool development?	Willing to modify package for benchmarking AR7-FT?
Yes	ESMValTool	ESMValTool	No	
Yes	ESMValTool, xarray etc	ESMValTool, xarray etc	Yes	Yes
Yes	ESMValTool	Will explore this		
Yes	ESMValTool	ESMValTool	Yes	Yes
Yes	Prepare, nctime	It will depend on which tools are available and compatible with the DR	No	
Yes	[Full comment in spreadsheet] E3SM Diags. MPAS-Analysis, hooks to other DOE packages such as PCMDI PMP and iLamb.	Same as current	Yes	No
Yes	CLIMAF, CESMEP, ESMValTool	At least CLIMAF CESMEP (built at national levels)	Yes	Yes
Yes	Grads, Gtool (Analysis/visualization software developed in-house)	It is possible to introduce ESMValTool or iLamb, or both.	No	
Yes	Beginning to use ESMValTool for model evaluation, use iLAMB for some land evaluation.	As current, plus own in-house tools.	Yes	Yes
Yes	NOAA MDTF, NCAR CVDP, PCMDI Metrics and, several years ago, iLAMB and ESMvalTool	Hope to use MB TT REF in addition to the ones above.	Yes	Yes
No, but within CMIP7 timeline		ESMValTool will be used for the AR7 Fast Track contribution.		
No, but within CMIP7 timeline		ESMValTool		

The Model Benchmarking TT are proposing to benchmark models (one simulation experiment at a time) as data are published in ESGF, would your centre/group be interested in using the benchmarking framework in your own computing environment?

Concerns raised include:

- The amount of work requested to implement it in our system, particularly the requirements relative to the intake of model's data.
- If the installation of the tools is easy it might be possible to do this for all simulations.
- Possibly, but it would depend on how easy or difficult it would be to incorporate the proposed benchmarking framework into our existing workflow. This is one of this case where the “devil is in the details”.
- Lack of personnel to implement/run benchmarking at home.
- Ease of installation in our computing environment and lack of human resources.
- Do not directly output all variables directly in CMORized netcdf. This is done as part of the model post processing workflow. We could still potentially use the benchmarking framework but would need to find a person time to do this.
- Sometimes current evaluation tool are not sufficient but are still very valuable for entire evaluation and benchmarking. Each modelling centre focuses on specific model schemes, current tools are required to extend to many biogeochemical variables and their interactions with atmospheric processes. Therefore, feel our own metrics which is utilized when we are developing and improving the model processes are also quite enough.
- Too hard to use and to port. Time is an issue.

Would your centre/group be willing to submit a preliminary time chunk of CMORised data from your piControl or any other experiment to allow a basic level of QC checks to be performed?

■ Yes, up to 2 years ■ Yes, 2-5 years ■ Yes, 5-10 years

Additional comments or questions on the Rapid Evaluation Framework?

- Like any community activity, there is always a concern about “unfunded mandates”. Preparing data for publication to ESGF is already a complex and onerous process for which the modeling centers bear the blunt of the cost. We would have to carefully evaluate cost and benefits of adding a “Rapid Evaluation Framework” layer to our existing workflow. This is especially the case in the current flat funding environment.
- It would need to be evaluated and quality controlled before publication. In particular, if this is used to exclude models from some analyses.
- Passed some concerns around this back to the TT. My concern is with "rapid" evaluation/benchmarking in general is the risk this just becomes a model beauty contest. This has the risk of stifling model development/ efforts to increase model realism. As a simple example, CMIP7 will have a number of models running in CO₂-emission mode. For the historical period this means atmospheric CO₂ is no longer prescribed, rather anthropogenic emissions are, and the resulting atmospheric CO₂ concentration will depend on the model simulated carbon sources and sinks. This means the atmospheric CO₂ (and all dependent variables) are less constrained to observations and thus will appear "worse" in a benchmarking exercise than models that use prescribed atmospheric CO₂. Yet, I would argue the CO₂-emission model are more suited for simulating future climate due to the fact they aim to fully simulate future climate - carbon cycle interactions. Similar risks hold for numerous other areas where, for making future projections having fully prognostic representation of variables and feedbacks would be preferred. This increases the freedom of the model and thus will penalize it, in a beauty contest against observations, against other models that are not prognostic and rather prescribe certain variables (e.g. atmospheric CO₂) based on observations. Other examples include: running with methane emissions, dynamic (prognostic) vegetation, prognostic and interactive fires, interactive ice sheets etc etc. It would be a great pity if a rapid benchmarking activity acted to decrease the development of models better suited for what we need them for; namely predicting the future, not looking good in the past. The latter is a necessary, but not sufficient condition, for predicting the future. I don't have an easier answer to this concern but wish to raise it.

Thank You

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